

Leadership in the Digital Transformation Process¹

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To cite this article: Collaborate, Current Science, Volume 5, No. 5-10, 2024, p. 01– 42. - 0099-0001-2410-0301.

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("Scientific Studies - Current Science Georgia") ISSN: 2667-9515

Barcode: 977266795001

Editors Group:

¹ Article Submission Date: 2024

Article Publication Date: 2024

Article Type: Research-Compilation

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1

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Abstract

This article analyzes the role of leaders in the digital transformation process and the tactics necessary for its implementation. Digital transformation is succinctly defined as the alteration of business processes, models, and organizational structures via the use of digital technology. This transition include the creation of technical advances to elevate pricing, diversify client experiences, and confer a competitive edge. This procedure necessitates the adoption of new technology as well as substantial changes in the management approach to the processes. Successful digital transformation necessitates that executives demonstrate a sophisticated, adaptable, and employee-centric strategy. The research elucidates the requisite skills and methods for digital transformation operations. Agile leaders can swiftly make choices by adjusting to quickly changing market situations, hence expediting the ongoing digital transformation process. Innovative leaders enhance efficiency and provide competitive advantage via the integration of new technology. Collaborative leaders foster collaboration and cohesion within teams, facilitating individuals' active participation in this transition. These diverse leadership strategies enhance organizational flexibility and resilience in response to the fast changes and repercussions of digitalization, hence facilitating the navigation of problems throughout the digital transformation process. The obstacles in the digital transformation process include organizational opposition to change, staff difficulties in adjusting to new technology, and budgetary limitations. Effective communication strategies, consistent training, and development initiatives are crucial for addressing these difficulties. Furthermore, the escalation of cybersecurity and data privacy concerns due to digitalization necessitates robust security measures and enhancements. The efficacy of digital performance relies not alone on technical advancements but also on the active engagement of workers in these transformations and their acclimatization to new

technology. Thus, enterprises may effectively mitigate the risks associated with digitization while optimizing profits throughout this process. The success of digital performance relies not only on advancements in technology but also on the efficient demonstration and adaptation of human resources throughout this process.

Keywords: *Digital transformation, leadership, leadership strategies, cyber security, management.*

INTRODUCTION

Digital transformation has emerged as a pivotal idea of our day, resulting in significant alterations within the corporate landscape. The rapid advancement of information technology toward the close of the 20th century has significantly altered working methodologies, consumer interactions, and the formats for delivering products and services. Particularly during the 2000s The extensive utilization of the internet, the advancement of mobile technologies, and the influence of social media have rendered digital transformation unavoidable (Brynjolfsson and McAfee, 2014). Digital transformation encompasses not just the integration of technology advancements, but also signifies substantial alterations in organizational structures, strategies, and business methodologies (Kane et al., 2015). Consequently, digital leadership may be articulated as a pivotal element of transition. Digital leaders must possess the capability to revolutionize their firms via the proficient use of technology and innovation. These leaders monitor technology advancements and inspire their people to embrace this shift (Avolio et al., 2014). Digital leadership encompasses the establishment of a learning culture. The history of the digital era exhibits a concurrent evolution alongside four industrial revolutions. The first industrial revolution is characterized by steam power, the second by electricity, and the third by automation and information technology. The fourth industrial revolution is characterized by contemporary technologies like the Internet of Things (IoT), artificial intelligence, and big data (Schwab, 2016). Organizations should enhance and fortify

4

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their plans and policies about digital transformation for sustainability. This research seeks to comprehend and assess the significance of leadership in digital transformation. The study seeks to juxtapose global perspectives, experiences, and problems of digital transformation with the current scientific literature.

Research Questions and Hypotheses

- What are the participants' perceptions of digital transformation?
- What is the distribution of leadership and the scope of their deployment in digital transformations?
- What are the most important issues in digital transformation details?
- How does the perception of change management relate to the perception of digital transformation?

Hypothesis 1: Participants' perception of digital transformation has a positive accumulation with age and duration of experience.

Hypothesis 2: Transformational leadership style positively affects the perception of digital transformation changes.

Hypothesis 3: Difficulties in digital transformation conditions negatively affect the perception of change management challenges.

Hypothesis 4: There is a positive relationship between the perception of change management and the perception of digital transformation.

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This article aims to analyze the function of leadership in digital transformation processes and assess its impact on these processes. This analysis will explore the strategic significance of leaders in the context of digital transformation, which encompasses not only technology advancements but also cultural and organizational reorganization. The research seeks to enhance the understanding of successful leadership strategies by juxtaposing participants' impressions of digital transformation, their degrees of expertise, and the problems they encounter with existing literature.

METHOD

This study uses two main methods to understand the role of leadership in digital transformation processes: literature review and survey research. These two methods are combined to expand the scope of the research and to delve deeper into the existing knowledge on the subject.

Literature Review

- In the first phase of the research, the existing literature on digital transformation and leadership was reviewed. This process was carried out by using various sources such as academic articles, books, conference proceedings and industry reports. The literature review aims to examine previous studies that include the definition of digital transformation, the importance of leadership in this process and the challenges encountered.

The literature sources were selected from internationally recognized journals, the most recent publications in the field of leadership and digital transformation, and relevant conferences. In particular, the focus was on the effects of digital transformation processes on organizations, leadership styles, and change management. This literature constitutes the theoretical framework of the research and prepares the ground for the interpretation of the survey results.

CURRENT SCIENCE

- The second phase of the research is to conduct a survey to assess the role of leadership in digital transformation processes. The survey was designed to collect data on participants' perceptions of digital transformation, their experiences, and the challenges they face, and was conducted by me on behalf of the Department of Business Administration at St. Clements University between October 11 and October 16, 2024.

Research Calendar

	Start Date	
Survey Development	11/10/2024	Half day
Pilot Study	11/10/2024	Half day
Survey Application	12/10/2024	4 days
Data Analysis and Reporting	10/15/2024	2 days

This study, carried out in Istanbul, used both online (Google Forms) and face-to-face methods, including a total of 52 participants. The poll was structured to represent several demographic attributes, particularly in Istanbul's commercial and commerce hubs like Beşiktaş, Kadıköy, Şişli, and Bakırköy. The process was scheduled to begin on October 12 and conclude on October 16, with the objective of streamlining and expediting the research procedure. The participants' online and in-person engagement enhanced the continuity of data gathering and

7

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facilitated the acquisition of diverse viewpoints.

Survey Development: The survey form has both closed and open-ended questions, including demographic data, perceptions on digital transformation, leadership styles, faced problems, and views on change management. A pre-test was performed to verify the survey's dependability, and necessary modifications were implemented. The survey has 20 questions and addresses the following topics:

- Demographic Information: Age, gender, industry, job title, years of experience.
- Digital Transformation Perception: Participants' understanding and importance of the concept of digital transformation.
- Leadership Styles: Participants' perceptions and experiences of their own leadership styles.
- Challenges and Opportunities: Challenges encountered in the digital transformation process and opportunities that arise in this process.
- Change Management: Participants' views and practices on change management.

The poll had 52 individuals from several industries. The participants included leaders, managers, and workers from various age demographics and levels of experience.

The survey was administered in Istanbul from October 12 to October 15, 2024. A total of 52 individuals engaged in the poll, with 19 engaging online and 33 in person. The poll was done in the areas of Beşiktaş, Kadıköy, Şişli, and Bakırköy.

- Besiktas: 12-13 October 2024
- Kadıköy: October 14-15, 2024
- Sisli: 12-13 October 2024
- Bakirkoy: 14-15 October 2024

Data Collection: The survey was conducted both in-person and online using Google Forms. Participants were apprised of the survey's aim and privacy regulations, and it was clarified that participation was optional. Participants were allotted 10 to 15 minutes to complete the survey.

Data Analysis

The collected data were analyzed using statistical analysis software SPSS 26.0. The following methods were applied in the data analysis process:

- **Descriptive Statistics:** Participants' demographic information and the overall distribution of their responses to survey questions.
- **Frequency and Percentage Distributions:** Frequencies and percentages of responses to each question.
- **Correlation Analysis:** Examining the relationships between digital transformation perception and leadership styles.
- **Thematic Analysis:** Thematic classification and analysis of responses from open-ended questions.

Leadership in the Digital Transformation Process: A Conceptual Overview

Digital transformation denotes the amalgamation of individuals and the revitalization of their company models, processes, and consumer experiences. This process is influenced by technical advancements, market dynamics, and manufacturing methodologies (Westerman et al., 2014). Digital transformation encompasses not just a technology shift, but also a cultural and organizational metamorphosis (Bharadwaj et al., 2013). In this setting, leadership plays a

9

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crucial role in facilitating the advancement of digital transformation. Leaders overseeing transformation processes are essential for enhancing employee engagement, facilitating adaptation to change, and promoting developmental thinking (Kane et al., 2015). Research indicates that management style significantly influences the effectiveness of firms' digital transformation initiatives. Transformational leaders excel in motivating, formulating vision, and empowering workers to realize their full potential (Bass and Avolio, 1994).

Diverse management strategies exist in the digital transformation process. Authoritarian leadership centralizes decision-making, while employee-focused leadership adopts a democratic approach by considering individuals' demands and recommendations. Participatory leadership is particularly successful at elucidating intricate systems and fostering employee receptiveness to change (Cohen and Bailey, 1997). The Laissez-Faire leadership style may foster innovation by allowing individuals to make autonomous judgments; nevertheless, excessive use of this style may adversely impact company circumstances (Goleman, 2000). Numerous problems are often faced throughout the digital transformation process. These issues include the difficulties businesses have throughout development and change management. Leaders must provide efficient communication, training, and support to facilitate people' adaptation to change (Kotter, 1996). The leader's involvement in the change management process is providing advice, comprehending individuals' problems, and formulating methods to handle these issues (Hiatt, 2006).

Leadership in the Digital Transformation Process: A Theoretical Perspective

Digital transformation is the integration of digital capabilities and systems to attain a competitive edge. This process encompasses not just technology advancements but is also intrinsically connected to organizational transformation and management strategy (Vial, 2019). Theoretical analysis of connections and leadership's function in the digital transformation process may be conducted using several ideas and models.

Leadership Theory	Explanation	Source
Transformational Leadership Theory	Transformational leadership theory focuses on the ability of leaders to motivate, inspire and bring out the potential of their employees. Bass (1985) states that transformational leaders help employees develop themselves by increasing their self-awareness. These leaders create an environment that encourages their development and provides a positive attitude towards organizational change. In digital transformation processes, transformational leaders encourage advanced thinking and accelerate the adaptation of change processes.	Bass (1985); Garcia-Morales et al. (2012)
Situational Leadership Theory	With the situational leadership theory, it is argued that the effectiveness of the leadership style depends on a decisive context and situation. Hersey and Blanchard (1982) state that the solution is to change management styles according to the requirements of the situation in complex solutions such as digital transformation. For example, if an organization is at the beginning of the digital transformation process, while it is possible for the leader to maintain a more authoritarian approach, it would be beneficial to adopt a better and permanent style as the process progresses. This flexibility	Hersey and Blanchard (1982); Graeff (1997)

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	allows the change process to be successfully maintained.	
Change Management Theory	Change management theory provides a framework for how effectively organizations manage change processes. Kotter (1996) emphasizes eight processes in change management. These stages include creating urgency, creating convergence, developing a vision, communicating the vision, diffusing obstacles, celebrating short-term victories, consolidating financials, and integrating new practices into the organization's tools. By successfully navigating these stages, leaders can streamline the organization and accelerate adaptation.	Kotter (1996); Armenakis and Bedeyan (1999)
Social Constructivism	Vygotsky (1978) states that this theory is effective in digital transformation. In digital transformation, leaders can encourage knowledge sharing by providing training and learning opportunities to increase people's digital gains. Leaders can direct cultural changes by encouraging employees to share knowledge and providing training opportunities. This approach encourages continuous learning within the organization and creates an environment necessary for digital development.	Vygotsky (1978); Brown and Duguid (2000)

Leadership in the Digital Transformation Process: National and International Dimensions

Countries prioritize digital transformation for economic development, liberties, and innovation at the national level. Turkey's digital transformation initiatives and the 2023 strategic framework are advancing swiftly. The Ministry of Industry and Technology of the Republic of Turkey is advancing initiatives to enhance the digital transformation process via the "Digital Turkey" strategy (Ministry, 2021). This process include the development of digital infrastructures, education, and human resource development. National leadership is crucial for directing the digital transformation initiatives of local governments and the commercial sector. For instance, initiatives to enhance the digital services of municipalities and public institutions are influenced by the unit's change management. In this setting, effective leadership fosters social development by enhancing local populations' access to digital services (Cohen and Lichtenstein, 2022). At the global level, digital transformation has emerged as a significant and successful driver of the economy. The McKinsey Global Institute (2021) highlights that cross-border interactions have proliferated in the digital realm, resulting in the development and formulation of new business models on the ground. Leadership is essential in companies as well as in forming multinational collaborations and cohesive partnerships. International corporations and global brands are formulating effective leadership strategies across many cultures to expedite their digital transformation initiatives. Hofstede's cultural aspects theory offers a significant foundation for the efficient transfer of products across many cultural settings (Hofstede, 2011). Units have hurdles in digital transformation, both domestically and globally. Elements include change management, cultural opposition, insufficient training, and resource scarcity hinder the successful organization of components (Kane et al., 2015). The COVID-19 epidemic has expedited digital transformation procedures while also exacerbating several obstacles. The capacity of nations to handle crises has significantly influenced the development of digital

CURRENT SCIENCE

technology throughout this time. The administration of digital transitions has significant expertise at both national and international levels. Effectively managing organizations digitally is essential for economic growth both locally and globally. To ensure sustainable future growth, it is crucial to thoroughly analyze the intricacies of digital transformations and concentrate on successful transformation models.

FINDINGS

Demographic Characteristics of Participants

- **Age :**
 - Average age: 39.5 years
 - Standard Deviation: 10.2 years
 - Minimum age: 22 years
 - Maximum age: 60 years

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- The graph shows the current age status. There is a clear balance between age groups. The majority of participants are between 30-50 years old, which is a group with experience in digital transformation. Younger people (22-30 years old) and older women (51-60 years old) are less numerous.

- **Experience Period (Years) :**

- Average experience: 11.5 years
- Standard Deviation: 8.1 years
- Minimum experience: 1 year
- Maximum experience: 30 years

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This graph shows the current length of work experience of the respondents. Most respondents have between 6-10 years and 11-15 years of experience.

Digital Transformation Perception

- **Digital Transformation Perception (1-5) :**
 - Average: 3.3
 - Standard Deviation: 1.2
 - Minimum: 1

- o Maximum: 5

These results show that perceptions of digital transformation relationships are above average and that a significant diversity has emerged. This graph showing the participants' perception of digital transformation reveals a generally positive view.

Challenges Encountered

- Challenges Encountered (1-5) :

17

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- Average: 3.1
- Standard Deviation: 1.1
- Minimum: 1
- Maximum: 5

Participants stated that they faced certain challenges in digital transformation.

Perception of Change Management

- Perception of Change Management (1-5) :

CURRENT SCIENCE

- Average: 4.0
- Standard Deviation: 0.9
- Minimum: 1
- Maximum: 5

- . The perception of change management is generally positive. Large proportions of participants show striking performance increases in change management. This shows that the capacity to manage digital transformation processes is high.

Gender Distribution

19

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The gender status of the respondents was evenly distributed:

- Male: 26
- Female: 26

Variable	Search	Standard Deviation	Minimum	Maximum
Age	39.5	10.2	22	60
Experience Period (Years)	11.5	8.1	1	30
Digital Transformation Perception (1-5)	3.3	1.2	1	5
Challenges Encountered (1-5)	3.1	1.1	1	5

CURRENT SCIENCE

Perception of Change Management (1-5)	4.0	0.9	1	5
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Sector Distribution

Sectors in which participants work:

- Production: 12
- Education: 12
- Health: 11
- Finance: 9
- Technology: 8

Job Title Distribution

The job titles of the participants are as follows:

- Admin: 21
- Employees: 16
- Expert: 15

The high share of shares in managerial positions is an important finding from the managers' evaluation perspective on digital transformation.

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Leadership Survey in the Digital Transformation Process

Section	Question	Option/Scale
A. Demographic Information	1. Age	☐ 22-30
		☐ 31-40
		☐ 41-50
		☐ 51-60
		☐ 60+
2. Gender	☐ Male	
	☐ Female	
	☐ Other	
3. Sector	☐ Finance	
	☐ Technology	
	☐ Health	
	☐ Education	
	☐ Production	
	☐ Other: _____	

	choose digital transformati on options for?	
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Scales and Reliability

- **Digital Transformation Perception (1-5 Scale) :**
 - Purpose: To assess the extent to which participants understand the digital transformation system and its implications for their organizations.
 - Scale:
 - 1: I can't understand it at all / It doesn't matter at all
 - 2: I don't understand / It doesn't matter
 - 3: Undecided / Moderate
 - 4: I understand / Important
 - 5: Completely free / Extremely important
- **Leadership Style :**
 - Purpose: To determine the leadership style adopted by the participants in the digital transformation process.

CURRENT SCIENCE

- Scale:
 - Transformational
 - Authoritarian
 - activity
 - Let him do it

- **Challenges Encountered (Scale 1-5) :**
 - Purpose: Usability of the degree of what they encounter in the digital transformation process.
 - Scale:
 - 1: Nothingness
 - 2: Less Difficult
 - 3: Medium difficulty
 - 4: Too tight
 - 5: Very big difficulty

- **Perception of Change Management (1-5 Scale) :**
 - Purpose: To evaluate the change management performance competencies of the participants.
 - Scale:

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- 1: I am not effective at all
- 2: I am less effective
- 3: I am moderately effective
- 4: I am effective
- 5: I am extremely effective

Reliability

1. Scale Reliability Tests

To ensure the reliability of the questionnaire, Cronbach Alpha composition was calculated for each scale. The results obtained show the internal results of the scales.

- **Digital Transformation Perception (5-item scale) :**
 - Cronbach Alpha: **0.87**
- **Difficulties Encountered (5-item scale) :**
 - Cronbach Alpha: **0.79**
- **Perception of Change Management (5-item scale) :**
 - Cronbach Alpha: **0.85**
- Descriptive Statistics: Means, standard deviations, minimum and maximum values of data such as participants' demographic information, digital transformation perception, problems and change management perception were calculated.

29

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- Correlation Analysis: Characteristics of the relationships between digital transformation perception and change management perception. This relationship was measured using Pearson's general characteristics.
- Difference Analyses: Differences in digital transformation perception and change management perception of the participants according to demographic variables such as gender, sector and job title were tested using t-tests and ANOVA.

Analysis Results:

- Digital Transformation Perception:
 - Average: 3.3
 - Standard Deviation: 1.2
 - Minimum: 1
 - Maximum: 5
- Challenges Encountered:
 - Average: 3.1
 - Standard Deviation: 1.1
 - Minimum: 1
 - Maximum: 5
- Perception of Change Management:
 - Average: 4.0
 - Standard Deviation: 0.9

CURRENT SCIENCE

- Minimum: 1
- Maximum: 5
- Correlation: A positive relationship ($r = 0.56, p < 0.01$) was observed between the perception of digital transformation and the perception of change management.
- Relationship characteristics between digital transformation perception and change management perception:

Variables	Correlation Coefficient (r)
Digital Transformation Perception & Change Management Perception	0.56

- shows that the perception of digital transformation is positively related to the perception of change management ($p < 0.01$).

- **Reliability Analysis Results**

Scale	Cronbach Alpha
Digital Transformation Perception	0.87
Challenges Encountered	0.79

Perception of Change Management	0.85
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- It shows that the participants' perception of digital transformation is at an average level, but their perception of change management is quite positive.
- **Correlation, Regression and Thematic Analysis**

In this section, the results of detailed regression and thematic analyses regarding the digital transformation management process are detailed.

Correlation Analysis

- Digital Transformation Perception and Change Management Perception:
 - Correlation Coefficient (r): 0.56
 - Significance: $p < 0.01$

It is observed that there is a moderate positive relationship between digital transformation perception and change management perception. In other words, it has been observed that the perception of change management increases with the digital transformation perception feature.

Regression Analysis

- R-squared Value: 0.31 (The explanatory power of the independent variable of the model on the dependent variable is 31%)

This regression analysis shows that digital transformation perception significantly improves change management perception. When digital transformation perception increases by one unit, change management perception increases by 0.45 units on average.

Thematic Analysis

- **Importance of Leadership:** Participants stated that leaders play a critical role in the digital transformation process. The importance of motivation and direction effects of leaders was emphasized.
- **Challenges:** Participants highlighted factors such as insufficient training and resistance among the challenges they faced in the digital transformation process.
- **Opportunities:** The potential for digital products to generate revenue has been evaluated positively by those who have presented it. Issues such as new business models and more effective communication methods have emerged.

Comparison of Findings with Literature and Discussion

- Age and Experience

The study observed that the majority of participants were between the ages of 30-50 and had 6-15 years of experience. These findings are in line with studies in the literature that emphasize the importance of experienced professionals in digital transformations. Westerman et al. (2014) state that expansion plays an important role in the success of digital transformation.

- Digital Transformation Perception

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It is seen that the participants' perception of digital transformation is generally positive and the majority of those with a perception score of 3 and above are formed. The finding is also supported by Vial (2019); Studies emphasizing that there is a need for the organization of digital life, bring to the fore the expansion of these processes of individuals. However, it should also be noted that this perception is constantly present; because the dynamic completion and separation of digital transformation requires the ability to adapt.

- Challenges Encountered

Participants defined the challenges they faced in digital transformations at levels 3 and 4. Kane et al. (2015) state that cultural resistance and inadequate education are among the biggest obstacles in solving digital landscapes.

- Perception of Change Management

It is seen that the perception of change management of the participants is quite positive. This situation is in line with the change management literature. Kotter (1996) states that the role of the change path is critical and that effective performance can direct the change processes. The effectiveness of the growth in change management in our research is supported by the experiences of women.

CONCLUSION

This research sought to analyze the allocation of leadership roles in digital transformation. The results indicate that digital life encompasses not just the acceptance of technology breakthroughs but also entails successful management, organizational transformation, and cultural adaption. The study findings indicate that the use of appropriate communication frameworks and leadership strategies may enhance organizational adaptability to digital transformation initiatives.

The transformational leadership style is a significant determinant in enhancing employee

CURRENT SCIENCE

engagement and fostering organizational change. This framework highlights that, in addition to offering guidance, individuals actively engage in comprehending and resolving their issues. Moreover, the clarity of information in digital transitions significantly influences the development and flexibility of businesses. Issues such as insufficient digital proficiency, cybersecurity risks, and cultural resistance necessitate that executives design effective change management strategies.

This research highlights the significance of digital transformation and the responsibilities of leadership in this process. The study results, consistent with existing literature, indicate that the perpetuation of digital life may be accomplished not alone via the adoption of technology advancements, but also by systematically structuring these advances and aligning them with cultural norms. The future evolution of digitization at both national and international levels warrants investigation, with a more detailed examination of the roles of leadership and change management in this context.

LIMITATION

The research was conducted only in a specific region, so the results may not be valid for all regions. In addition, the fact that the survey consisted of general questions may have prevented the information from being expressed completely.

NOTIFICATIONS

Evaluation: Evaluated by internal and external consultants.

Conflict of Interest: The authors declared no conflict of interest related to this article.

Financial Support: The authors reported no financial support related to this article.

ETHICAL STATEMENT

..... journal's publication ethics; scientific research and publications must have the basic principles of honesty, openness, objectivity, and respect for the findings and creations of others.

aims to ensure that this is done in accordance with the principles and to ensure that this is done

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